

A Study on the Determinants of Organic Food Purchase Intention by Adult Consumers in Kolkata

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Purpose: The objective of the study is to evaluate how health, environment, awareness, affordability, taste and preferences influence Indian consumers' intention to buy organic food.

Methodology / Design: A descriptive research design was employed. Data were collected through structured questionnaires distributed among urban consumers in India. The responses were analysed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis to examine the influence of key factors on purchase intentions.

Findings: Results indicate that health and taste considerations exert the strongest influence on buying decisions, while environmental and ethical concerns play a supporting role. Price and insufficient awareness remain major barriers to wider adoption.

Limitations: The study is limited to urban respondents and a moderate sample size, which may reduce its general applicability across rural populations.

Practical Implications: The findings provide guidance for marketers and policymakers to highlight health and taste benefits in promotional strategies, while simultaneously working to address cost and knowledge-related barriers.

Value / Originality: This research enriches the limited body of work on organic consumer behaviour in India by offering empirical evidence from an emerging market, thereby contributing to a better understanding of how demographic and attitudinal factors shape organic food adoption.

Keywords: Organic Food, Environmental Concern, Health Consciousness, Purchases Intention

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1. Introduction

According to Muhammad, Rushi, and Hashim (2014), organic foods are those that have not been treated with any synthetic inputs during processing. Products labelled as "organic" have been manufactured and kept without the use of any synthetically generated additives, as verified by a third-party certification agency. Organic food has the potential to be more nutritious than conventionally produced food, which is one of the main advantages. Another benefit of organic food is its environmental sustainability. The continuous rise in affluence and improved living standards has transformed modern lifestyles, contributing to accelerated patterns of consumption. This surge in demand has been directly associated with multiple environmental challenges, including climate change, biodiversity loss, and resource depletion (Jackson, 2009; Princen, 2002). Scholars argue that unsustainable consumption practices are now among the most pressing drivers of ecological degradation, threatening the stability of planetary systems (Rockström et al., 2009; Steffen et al., 2015). In response to these concerns, organic agriculture has emerged as a popular alternative to conventional food production, offering both health and environmental benefits. Organic farming avoids synthetic fertilizers, pesticides, and genetically modified organisms, thereby reducing exposure to chemical residues while promoting ecological balance (Willer & Lernoud, 2019; Kahl et al., 2012). Systematic reviews have highlighted that while organic foods do not always provide superior nutrient content, they are widely perceived as safer and healthier options (Smith-Spangler et al., 2012; Mie et al., 2017). Furthermore, sustainable diets incorporating organic foods are increasingly emphasized as crucial for improving public health and mitigating environmental pressures associated with industrialized agriculture (Johnston et al., 2014; Vermeir & Verbeke, 2006).

Over the last several years, the market for organic foods has exploded. According to a 2021 study conducted by the FiBL (Forschungsinstitut für Biologischen Landbau), India is in a category of its own among the 187 nations that engage in organic farming. India is home to over 30% of the world's organic farmers (FiBL & IFOAM, 2021). It exports organic oilseeds, processed foods, cereals, and millets to other countries like Europe,

the United States, Canada, and Korea. India exported organic food in the 2015-16 fiscal year worth 298 million dollars and is ranked at number 5 in terms of increase in organic land.

As more people in India learn about the advantages of buying organic food, the percentage who intends to do so has been rising gradually. The ASSOCHAM has released research predicting a 25% CAGR for the market of organic food in India between 2021 and 2026 (ASSOCHAM, 2021). Multiple factors, including increased consumer health awareness and desire for chemical-free and ecologically friendly food items, have contributed to this expansion.

Rising consumer knowledge and concern about food quality and safety have contributed to a growth in the desire to buy organic food in Kolkata, India. Increased health and environmental concern, as well as a desire to support local farmers, are contributing to a change in consumer attitudes in Kolkata, a city recognised for its varied population and culinary legacy. Consumers in Kolkata are actively seeking organic alternatives due to the perceived health benefits, environmental sustainability, and the desire to connect with local food sources (Bose, 2022). Moreover, the concept of "farm-to-table" and the desire for locally sourced food have gained prominence among the residents of Kolkata. This development sheds light on the shifting tastes and increasing demand for organic food in Kolkata, India, opening up doors for local farmers, retailers, and entrepreneurs to meet the demands of conscientious shoppers and improve the city's food system.

2. Literature Review

There has been a meteoric rise in recent years in both consumer interest and demand for organic food items. What motivates consumers to choose organic goods has been the subject of much research. The goal of this thematic literature review is to survey and synthesise research on the factors that motivate people to purchase organic food. The goal of this study is to examine the key trends and discoveries in the literature on the subject of what drives people to buy organic food.

Purchase Intention

Purchase intention represents an individual's conscious plan or willingness to purchase a particular product in the future.

Within the organic food sector, it has been regarded as one of the most reliable predictors of actual consumer behaviour, as intention often precedes and shapes the final decision-making process (Garg, Narwal, & Kumar, 2024). Scholars highlight that in the context of sustainable and ethical consumption, purchase intention does not merely reflect an economic choice but also embodies psychological, social, and cultural values (Yadav & Pathak, 2016). Empirical evidence suggests that consumers who exhibit stronger purchase intentions are more likely to translate these intentions into actual buying behaviours, provided that external barriers such as limited availability or higher prices do not intervene (Asif et al., 2018). In many developing economies, including India, the growing recognition of health and environmental benefits has substantially elevated the role of purchase intention in shaping demand for organic products (Bazhan, 2024). Trust has also emerged as a crucial determinant in strengthening the link between purchase intention and actual purchase. Since organic food markets are vulnerable to scepticism about certification and labelling, consumers with greater trust in organic claims demonstrate significantly higher levels of purchase intention (Nguyen, Lobo, & Greenland, 2019). Furthermore, socio-demographic factors such as education and income positively reinforce intention, making it a multidimensional construct influenced by personal beliefs, product knowledge, and social pressures (Sogari, Pucci, Aquilani, & Zanni, 2021). Overall, purchase intention serves as the cornerstone of consumer decision-making in the organic food sector. It not only reflects consumers' readiness to act but also integrates psychological motivation with contextual influences, making it a pivotal construct in understanding sustainable consumption patterns.

Health Concern

Health concern is a primary driver influencing consumers' decision to purchase organic products. Individuals who prioritise their well-being are more likely to choose organic food because it is perceived as healthier, safer, and free from harmful chemicals (Pino, Peluso, & Guido, 2012). Numerous studies demonstrate that health-conscious consumers often regard organic food as an investment in long-term wellness rather than a short-term dietary choice (Aertsens et al., 2011). Recent findings reveal that heightened awareness of food-related health risks, including pesticide residues and artificial additives,

motivates consumers to express stronger intentions to purchase organic alternatives (Zagata, 2012). In addition, the COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated health concerns, prompting individuals to reassess their food choices and increasingly favour organic options (Sharma & Foropon, 2022). Health concern is not limited to individual well-being but extends to family health, where parents show stronger preferences for organic products to ensure food safety for their children (Prentice, Chen, & Wang, 2019). Moreover, in emerging economies like India, health-related concerns often outweigh environmental motivations, underscoring the significance of health in shaping organic food consumption behaviour (Garg et al., 2024). Collectively, evidence confirms that health concern remains one of the most powerful psychological motivators for organic food purchase intention, transcending demographic and cultural boundaries.

Affordability

Affordability is a significant barrier to widespread adoption of organic products. Organic food is often priced higher than conventional alternatives due to costly certification processes, smaller production scales, and higher input costs (Hughner et al., 2007). For price-sensitive consumers, affordability strongly influences purchase intention and frequently limits the actual consumption of organic food (Aschemann-Witzel & Zielke, 2017). Research highlights that while health and environmental concerns encourage intention, the higher cost of organic products reduces purchase frequency, particularly in developing economies where disposable incomes are limited (Moser, 2016). However, as consumers' purchasing power rises, affordability concerns tend to diminish, and organic food demand grows steadily (Paul & Rana, 2012). Studies further reveal that younger consumers and students often express willingness to buy organic products but face affordability constraints that hinder regular consumption (Nuttavuthisit & Thøgersen, 2017). Price fairness also plays a role: when consumers perceive organic food prices as justified by quality and benefits, affordability becomes less of a barrier (Sirieix, Kledal, & Sulitang, 2011). Therefore, affordability remains a critical determinant shaping consumer decisions, particularly in countries where organic markets are still emerging. Addressing price sensitivity through subsidies, discounts, or value communication can significantly enhance organic food adoption.

Environmental Consciousness

Environmental consciousness has emerged as a central determinant of sustainable consumer behaviour, particularly in the organic food sector. Consumers who demonstrate higher awareness of ecological issues often exhibit stronger preferences for products that minimise harm to the environment (Joshi & Rahman, 2019). This is reflected in their willingness to adopt organic food, which is widely associated with eco-friendly farming practices, reduced chemical inputs, and biodiversity preservation (Grunert et al., 2014). Research shows that environmental consciousness influences not only attitudes but also perceived moral obligations, leading to ethical consumer choices (Biswas & Roy, 2015). In addition, eco-conscious individuals tend to perceive organic food consumption as an extension of their environmental values, thereby reinforcing purchase intentions (Nguyen, Lobo, & Greenland, 2019). Studies conducted in developing nations highlight that environmental concern is gradually increasing as a motivator, though health remains more dominant (Bazhan, 2024). The effect of environmental consciousness is also mediated by trust and labelling: when eco-labels are credible and transparent, consumers with high environmental concern display a significantly greater likelihood of choosing organic products (Schäufele & Hamm, 2018). Thus, environmental consciousness not only drives organic food adoption but also strengthens the sustainability discourse by linking individual consumer choices with broader ecological outcomes.

Awareness

Awareness of organic food plays a pivotal role in shaping consumer intention and purchase behavior. Awareness encompasses knowledge of what organic food is, how it is produced, and the health or environmental benefits it provides (Magnusson et al., 2001). Consumers with higher awareness are more likely to recognise the value of organic products and express stronger purchase intentions (Asif et al., 2018). Studies in emerging markets highlight that limited awareness remains a key barrier to organic food adoption, as many consumers either confuse organic with natural products or lack trust in certification systems (Misra & Singh, 2016). However, targeted awareness campaigns and labelling efforts have been shown to significantly enhance consumer confidence and willingness to purchase (Hughner et al., 2007).

Research also shows that awareness interacts with socio-demographic factors: educated and urban consumers tend to exhibit higher levels of awareness and, consequently, higher purchase intentions (Sogari et al., 2021). Moreover, awareness not only strengthens purchase intention directly but also moderates the relationship between health/environmental concerns and actual buying behaviour (Yadav & Pathak, 2016). Overall, awareness serves as a foundational driver that informs consumer perceptions and mitigates scepticism, thereby bridging the gap between intention and actual consumption.

Taste and Preference

Taste and sensory preference are fundamental aspects of consumer food choice, and they significantly shape attitudes toward organic food. While health and environmental motivations are often highlighted, studies indicate that taste remains a decisive factor in whether consumers repeatedly purchase organic products (Hughner et al., 2007). Consumers tend to perceive organic food as fresher and more flavourful compared to conventional alternatives (Schleenbecker & Hamm, 2013). Research shows that positive sensory experiences strengthen loyalty and encourage habitual consumption of organic products (Zanoli & Naspetti, 2002). Conversely, when organic products fail to meet taste expectations, consumers are less likely to sustain their buying behaviour, even if health or environmental benefits are recognised (Bryła, 2016). Preferences also differ across demographics: younger consumers emphasise novelty and taste variety, while older consumers value authenticity and freshness (Grunert, 2005). Cultural factors further influence preferences, as local traditions and cuisines shape perceptions of taste in organic foods (Naspetti & Zanoli, 2009). Thus, taste and preference not only influence trial behaviour but also play a critical role in sustaining long-term demand for organic products, making them indispensable considerations in marketing strategies.

3. Research Problem

Few research has looked at whether or not people in Kolkata, India, plan on purchasing organic food. Despite Kolkata's large population and diversity, research on the variables that influence shoppers' decisions to purchase organic food in this setting is scant.

Understanding the unique dynamics and preferences of adult consumers in Kolkata is crucial for developing targeted strategies to promote organic food consumption in this urban setting. Besides, there is a need to explore the awareness and perception of organic food benefits among consumers in Kolkata, as well as the barriers they face when considering organic food purchases. By providing light on the regional elements that affect consumers' choices to purchase organic food, research in this field will close a knowledge gap. This will inform marketing strategies, product development, and policy initiatives aimed at encouraging sustainable and healthy food choices among Kolkata residents.

4. Objectives of the Study

1. To analyse the factors that influence consumers' purchase intention towards organic food products.
2. To examine the relationship among the identified factors and consumers' purchase intention towards organic food products.

5. Research Methodology

5.1 Research Framework

The link between the dependent and independent variables is defined using the research framework in figure 1. The research problem and literature review of the study informed the following research design: purchase intent as the dependent variable; health concerns, affordability, environmental consciousness, and knowledge of taste and preference as independent variables.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework of the Study

5.2 Research Hypothesis

The hypotheses that are formulated examine the connections between the independent factors and the dependent variable as follows. In this study there are five hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant relationship between health concern and consumer purchase intention.

Hypothesis 2: There is a significant relationship between affordability and consumer purchase intention.

Hypothesis 3: There is a significant relationship between awareness and influence and consumer purchase intention.

Hypothesis 4: There is a significant relationship between environmental concern and consumer purchase intention.

Hypothesis 5: There is a significant relationship between taste and preference and consumer purchase intention.

5.3 Data Collection

The distribution of questionnaires has provided the majority of the survey data. The first section of the questionnaire asked about socio-demographic factors like gender, age, etc., while the second section asked closed-ended questions about scale items like the desire to buy organic food. For this, a Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) was used. A preliminary pilot sample was used to evaluate the questionnaire's validity and clarity.

5.4 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

This research is a descriptive study in which a probabilistic random sampling method is used. In the study, primary data from approximately 500 respondents who were 18 years of age and above were collected. To determine the appropriate sample size, Cochran's formula has been applied, considering a confidence level of 95 % (Cochran, W.G., 2007). By screening the data through a random number generator, 385 valid random cases was selected as samples, ensuring a random representative selection process.

The target population of the study are the consumers residing in Kolkata selected randomly, and we have collected the data from various diverse locations within Kolkata chosen randomly during random time intervals. By using random sampling, we aimed to increase the likelihood that our sample accurately represents the characteristics of the entire population in Kolkata.

This approach helps to minimise selection bias and enhance the reliability and applicability of our conclusions and inferences to the population as a whole. The randomness in participant selection and data collection allows for a more comprehensive understanding of consumer behaviour in Kolkata, enabling us to draw meaningful insights and make relevant recommendations.

5.5 Data Analysis

The statistical programme SPSS is used to examine a pool of data after it was collected from the representative sample of the population. The goal of the analysis is to put the theory to the test. Factor analysis was utilised as a method to organise related questions into their corresponding representative variables in order to streamline the data. A Cronbach's alpha reliability test has been performed to guarantee dependability. This helped in determining if the variables accurately reflect the construct that they are meant to represent. Multiple linear regression was used to look at the connection between the dependent and independent variables after the dependability of the variables had been determined. By this, we verified the theories and determined if the connection is statistically significant.

6. Analysis and Findings

Descriptive Statistics and Measurements

A descriptive analysis of the study's sample revealed that 314 (or 81.3%) of the 365 respondents were male and 74 (19.2%) were female. In terms of age group, 16.1% of respondents were aged between 18 and 24 years (n=62), 53.9% of respondents were aged between 25 and 34 years (n=208), 24.4% of respondents were aged between 34 and 44 years (n=94), and 6.2% of respondents were above 44 (n=24). As per the marital status, 37.8% were single (n=146), 61.9% were married (n=239), and 0.3% were divorced (n=1). According to the educational qualification, 32.1% were from graduation level (n=124), 58.8% were from master's level (n=227), 6.2% were from doctoral level (n=24) and 3.4% were from other backgrounds (n=13). Occupation-wise, 17.6% were students (n=68), 46.6% were service persons (n=180), 3.1% were homemakers (n=12), 0.5% were retired (n=2), and 1.8% were from other occupations. Lastly, 8.5% had a family income less than 20000 (n=33), 13% were from the income group 20000-40000 (n=50),

13% were from the income group 40000-60000 (n=50), 11.1% were from the income group 60000-80000 (n=43), and 54.9% belonged to the income group above 80000 (n=212).

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.936	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	6313.509
	Df	378
	Sig.	.000

Table 1: KMO and Bartlett's Test

In table 1: Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin is used to evaluate the data's suitability for factor analysis in terms of sampling. It may take on values between 0 and 1, with anything over 0.6 suggesting sufficient sampling. Our KMO value of .936 is statistically significant (p=.000) and verifies sampling adequacy. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, which assumes that the correlation matrix of the variables is an identity matrix, is used to test the null hypothesis that there is no connection between the variables. Since the test is statistically significant (p < 0.05), component analysis is possible since the correlation matrix is not an identity matrix.

Factor Analysis

Rotated Component Matrix ^a	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
I am willing to pay more for organic food because it is healthier			.979		
I believe that organic food is healthier than conventionally grown food.			.945		
I am concerned about the environmental impact of food production.					.932
I care about the welfare of animals used in food production.					.897
I am influenced by the labeling and marketing of organic food.					.892
I purchase organic food regularly.					.887
I actively seek out organic food options when shopping.			.886		
I prioritize organic food over non-organic options when making food choices.			.874		
I feel good about myself when I purchase organic food.			.868		
I think organic food tastes better than non-organic food.					.867
I believe that organic food is more nutritious than non-organic food.					.867
I am willing to sacrifice convenience for the sake of purchasing organic food.					.862
I consider the environmental impact of food production when I making food choices.					.852
I consider the welfare of animals used in food production when making food choices.					.844
I am more likely to purchase organic food if it is locally produced.			.833		
I am more likely to purchase organic food if it is labeled as eco-friendly.					.824
I am more likely to purchase organic food if it is labeled as natural.					.824
I am more likely to purchase organic food if it is labeled as free from pesticides or chemicals.					.782
I am more likely to purchase organic food if it is labeled as humanely raised.					.699
I will continue to consume organic food without being affected by the price changes.			.694		
I am willing to pay a higher price for organic food.			.679		
I don't mind spending more time sourcing for organic food.			.660		
Buying organic food is a smart thing to do even if they cost more.			.615		
I am willing to organic food as the benefits are more than the cost.			.608		
I am influenced by the recommendations of friends and family when it comes to purchasing organic food.					.602
I am influenced by the recommendations of health professionals when it comes to purchasing organic food.					.612
I am influenced by the recommendations of environmental organizations when it comes to purchasing organic food.					.732
I am influenced by media coverage of organic food when it comes to purchasing organic food.					.779
I am influenced by the availability and accessibility of organic food when it comes to purchasing organic food.					.692

Table 2: Rotated Component Matrix

A statistical technique called factor analysis is used to determine if a group of variables may be regarded as independent while yet reflecting a broader set of related variables. It allows for a huge dataset to be broken down into a smaller collection of variables. In this research, we used PCA to determine and categorise the most important factors that warranted further exploration. In table 2, five independent variables were derived from the results: health concerns, affordability, awareness, environmental consciousness, taste and preference. The customers' desire to buy organic food was the specified dependent variable employed for this study.

Using this method, we were able to obtain a deeper comprehension of what motivates people to buy organic products. Five variables with values greater than 1 were identified using the scree plot, which together accounted for 64.243% of the total variance explained in our study. Insights into the underlying structure of the data and the direction for factor retention may be gained from this.

Reliability Test

To establish the accuracy of measurements, a reliability test is performed to evaluate the regularity and dependability of each factor. Cronbach's alpha was used to determine the average correlation between survey questions. This coefficient, whose value ranges from zero to one, is used to measure trustworthiness. Our results were examined for consistency across five distinct variables using Cronbach's alpha. The computed Cronbach's alpha values for each variable are listed below:

Cronbach's alpha coefficients

Variables	No. of Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Health Concern	10	.908
Awareness	5	.939
Affordability	7	.880
Environmental Consciousness	3	.698
Taste and Preference	2	.616

Table 3: Cronbach's alpha coefficients

According to the findings in table 3, all of the research variables have a good internal consistency and may be trusted, with a minimum acceptable Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.60 (Hair et al., 2003). This suggests that the measurements taken for each variable are consistent and dependable. Overall, our analysis demonstrates that the survey instrument used in this study is reliable for assessing these variables.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis is a statistical technique that looks at the relationship between a single dependent variable and a large number of possible independent variables. Multiple linear regressions were used to assess the effects of the five independent variables (health concerns, affordability, awareness, environmental consciousness, taste and preference) on purchase intention for organic food products.

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.716a	0.512	0.506	0.7081	1.704

Table 4: Model Summary

The value of the multiple correlation coefficients R between the predictors and the outcome was found to be 0.716, indicating a moderately strong relationship in table 4. With an R² value of 0.512, we may infer that the dependent variable accounts for around 51.20 per cent of the variance in the independent variables. Additionally, the adjusted R² value, which assesses the generalisability of the model, was determined to be 0.506. The small difference of 0.006 between the adjusted R² and R² values suggests that the model has good generalization capability. To evaluate the assumption of independent errors, the Durbin-Watson statistic was employed, which yielded a value of 1.704. As it is near to the ideal number of 2, it suggests that the assumption of independent mistakes is likely satisfied, making this a preferable value.

Anova Test

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-Ratio	Sig.
Regression	199.116	5	39.823	79.432	0.000b
Residual	189.509	378	.501		
Total	388.625	383			

Table 5: ANOVA TEST

The findings in table 5 considerably improve our capacity to predict the outcome variable, according to the F-ratio calculation, which showed a value of 79.432 with a significance level of 0.000 (P < 0.05).

Coefficient Test

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	St Error	Beta		
(constant)	3.906	.036		108.108	0.000
Health Concern	.347	.036	.344	9.579	0.000
Affordability	-.355	.036	-.353	-9.815	0.000
Awareness	.504	.036	.500	13.930	0.000
Environmental Consciousness	.103	.036	.102	2.835	0.005
Taste and Preference	.096	.036	.095	2.643	0.009

Table 6: Coefficient Test

In table 6, we may comprehend the link between the predictor and outcome based on the unstandardised coefficients. A favourable association is denoted by a positive coefficient. The unstandardised coefficients also provide additional information about how much each predictor affects the result when all other predictors are equal. The predictor is significantly contributing to the model when the value of Sig. is less than 0.05. Additionally, the larger the predictor's contribution to the model is, the lower the value of significance.

The unstandardised coefficients for health concerns show that as consumers' worry for their health rises by one unit, their desire to buy organic food increases by .347 units, according to the study. The predictor is likewise significant since the Sig level is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$).

The unstandardised affordability coefficients is -.355, the t-value is -9.815, and the significance level is 0.05; for every one-unit increase in affordability, consumer willingness to purchase decreases by 0.355. This predictor is statistically significant at a level of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$).

The unstandardised coefficients of awareness .504 with a t-value of 13.930, respectively, suggest that when customer awareness rises by one unit, their purchase intention rises by .504 unit. Given that the value of Sig is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$), awareness is clearly a significant predictor.

The unstandardised coefficients for environmental consciousness are 0.103, 2.835, and 0.05, respectively. This implies that as a consumer's awareness of the environment increases by one unit, their desire to buy increases by 0.220 units. Given that the predictor's value of Sig is 0.005 ($p < 0.05$), we may conclude that it is significant.

The unstandardised coefficients for taste and preferences 0.096 a t-value 2.643 and a p-value 0.05 indicate that when customers' taste and desire for organic food rise by one unit, their intention to buy it increases by 0.189 units. We may infer that taste and preference are important predictors since Sig is 0.009 ($p < 0.05$).

In summary, the equation for Purchase Intention (PI) based on the regression analysis is as follows:

$$PI = (3.906 \text{ CONSTANT}) + (0.347 \text{ HEALTH CONCERN}) + (-0.355 \text{ AFFORDABILITY}) + (0.504 \text{ AWARENESS}) + (0.103 \text{ ENVIRONMENTAL CONSCIOUSNESS}) + (0.096 \text{ TASTE AND PREFERENCE}).$$

Using this equation, we may make educated guesses about how likely we are to buy organic food items given the values of the aforementioned independent variables.

7. Findings

Results of Hypothesis Testing

HYPOTHESIS	VARIABLES	REMARKS
Ho1	There is no significant relationship between health concerns and consumers' purchase intentions.	REJECTED
Ha1	There is a significant relationship between health concerns and consumers' purchase intentions.	ACCEPTED
Ho2	There is no significant relationship between affordability and consumers' purchase intention	REJECTED
Ha2	There is a significant relationship between affordability and consumers' purchase intention	ACCEPTED
Ho3	There is no significant relationship between awareness and consumers' purchase intention.	REJECTED
Ha3	There is a significant relationship between awareness and consumers' purchase intention.	ACCEPTED
Ho4	There is no significant relationship between environmental concern and consumers' purchase intention.	REJECTED
Ha4	There is a significant relationship between environmental concern and consumers' purchase intention.	ACCEPTED
Ho5	There is no significant relationship between taste and preference and consumers' purchase intention.	REJECTED
Ha5	There is a significant relationship between taste and preference and consumers' purchase intention	ACCEPTED

Table 7: Results of Hypothesis Testing

Table 7 : Illustrates that the independent variables Health Concern, Affordability, Awareness, Environmental Consciousness, Taste and Preference showed significant value at the $p < 0.05$ level; therefore, all five hypotheses were accepted, while the null hypothesis got rejected.

Ha1: There exists a positive and significant correlation between health concerns and consumers' intention to purchase organic food.

The unstandardised coefficient for health is 0.347, with a t-value of 9.579 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). This lends credence to the health-consciousness concept.

Ha2: There is a significant relationship between affordability and consumers' purchase intention. The unstandardised coefficient of -0.355, the t-value of -9.815, and the p-value of 0.000 point to affordability being a major factor in the conclusion that it should be adopted. There is a negative correlation between the cost of organic items and customers' desire to purchase them, implying that as prices increase, fewer people would choose to buy organic food.

Ha3: There is a significant relationship between awareness and consumers' purchase intention. Acceptability is ensured by awareness's substantial unstandardised coefficients (0.504, $t=13.930$, $p=0.000$). The results lead us to conclude that there is a favourable relationship between consumers' level of knowledge and their propensity to purchase organic food. Standardised coefficients of 0.500 denote the highest beta among the five variables. Awareness may have a significant impact on whether or not those customers will choose to make organic food purchases.

Ha4: There exists a significant and positive relationship between environmental consciousness and consumers' purchase intention. The unstandardised coefficient is 0.103, the t-value is 2.835, and the p-value is 0.005, the factor being a significant one; hence, the hypothesis is accepted. The demand for organic food will rise as customers learn more about the benefits of these goods.

Ha5: There is a positive and significant relationship between consumers' taste and preference and their purchase intention. It is considered to be statistically significant since its unstandardised coefficient is 0.96, t-value is 2.643, and p-value is 0.009. Customers are more likely to buy organic foods because of their affinity for these items.

8. Conclusion

The results of the research show that each of the five independent variables—affordability, awareness, health concern, environmental consciousness, taste and preference significantly correlates with the dependent variable, purchase intention.

Since the alternative hypotheses were accepted and the null hypotheses were rejected, the research goals and hypotheses were satisfactorily tested.

The results show a strong correlation between intentions to buy organic food and environmental awareness, health concerns, awareness, affordability, taste and preference. However, affordability is the only factor that has a detrimental effect on the dependent variable. The overall R^2 score of 0.512 (51.20%) for all independent variables indicates a modest connection. In other words, 51.20 % of the difference in purchase intention may be attributed to factors such as affordability, knowledge and influence, health concerns, environmental awareness, and taste and preference.

As shown by its highest beta value of 0.504, awareness stands out as a particularly significant component among all the variables evaluated in this study. The value of consumer knowledge and social networks in influencing their propensity to buy organic food is highlighted by this research. Managers in the organic food sector need to be aware of the effect of customers' social networks, including referrals from friends, family, and social media influences. Managers must continually provide excellent customer service and premium organic items in order to promote favourable word-of-mouth. Collaboration with well-known persons or groups in the organic food industry may improve brand credibility and recognition even further. Organic food sellers may explore the strength of customer networks and use them to increase purchase intention by giving awareness-building efforts top priority.

According to its beta value of 0.347, health consciousness is an important element that greatly affects buying intention. According to the research, customers who value their health are more likely to have a strong desire to buy organic food. This emphasises how crucial it is for merchants of organic foods to focus their marketing efforts on emphasising the health advantages of using organic goods. Retailers may successfully entice health-conscious customers and increase their buying intention by emphasising the possible health benefits, such as less exposure to pesticides and chemical additives. Retailers may also consider offering informational materials and educational tools to better teach customers about the advantages of eating organic food for their health.

By implementing these tactics into practice, businesses may encourage better lifestyles and sustainable food choices while luring customers who are health-conscious.

Environmental concern, with a beta value of 0.103, ranks third in influencing purchase intention. Despite being relatively smaller compared to other predictors, its effect remains statistically significant, suggesting that consumers' awareness and sensitivity toward environmental issues play a meaningful role in shaping their buying behavior. This finding highlights that individuals who prioritise sustainability and ecological responsibility are more inclined to consider organic products. Therefore, businesses in the organic sector can strategically leverage this segment by emphasising the environmental benefits of their products—such as reduced carbon footprint, eco-friendly packaging, and sustainable sourcing. Strengthening marketing campaigns around these themes not only resonates with environmentally conscious consumers but also enhances the brand's image as socially responsible, which in turn can further stimulate demand.

With a beta value of 0.096, taste and preference still have a significant influence on purchase intention despite ranking fourth. This suggests that customers' individual tastes and preferences influence whether they choose to buy organic food. It is essential for sellers of organic foods to comprehend and accommodate the varied tastes and preferences of their target client. Offering a broad variety of organic food alternatives, marketing distinctive flavours and culinary experiences linked with organic goods, and doing consumer research to determine particular taste preferences among various customer categories may all help accomplish this. Retailers may improve their attractiveness and raise purchase intention among consumers of organic food by matching their product offers to customers' tastes.

Affordability, with a beta value of -0.355, on the other hand, was shown to have a negative connection with the dependent variable. This suggests that for some customers, the cost of organic food is a substantial barrier, possibly reducing their desire to make a purchase. Managers and retailers must put measures in place to increase the accessibility and affordability of organic goods for a larger variety of customers in order to solve this problem.

To lower total pricing, this may include investigating cost-saving strategies in the manufacturing, distribution, and marketing processes. In addition, emphasising the value and long-term advantages of buying organic goods, such as better health outcomes or environmental sustainability, might assist customers in justifying the higher initial expenses. Retailers may get through the cost barrier and boost purchase intent across a wider customer base by lowering the price of organic food and highlighting its value proposition.

Limitations of the Study

Although this research offers useful information on the variables affecting the desire to buy organic food, there are a number of issues that need to be addressed. First of all, the study's reliance on self-reported data from a small sample size may have limited the results' applicability to a broader population. Furthermore, since the study's primary emphasis was on local customers, the findings may not be generalisable to people from other cultural backgrounds or geographic locations. The findings are also relevant for this specific time period, so extrapolating them beyond that point may not be a good idea. Additionally, the research did not fully address contextual or situational variables, which may potentially have a substantial impact, and instead focused exclusively on the effect of individual characteristics on the desire to buy organic foods. Finally, the present study considers the broad class of organic food products in general. Hence, upcoming studies may cover specific lines of products, such as spices, beverages, etc. Future research could consider employing larger and more diverse samples, exploring cross-cultural differences, and incorporating a broader range of factors to provide a comprehensive understanding of organic food purchase intention.

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